

MORPHOLOGY AND HISTOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF BRAIN TISSUE IN ACUTE INTOXICATION PSYCHOSIS.

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Relevance of the topic: Psychosis is a basic concept in psychiatry. It used to be the same name for all kinds of mental illnesses. Today, the term describes an ill-defined complex symptom (syndrome) characterized by hallucinations, delusions, loss of reality, or ego disturbances. In some diseases, affective symptoms are also associated with psychoses. These different symptoms can occur individually or in combination.

Psychoses can occur in various diseases. Diagnosis of the disease is possible only through careful diagnosis. Therapy depends on the disease and symptoms. If there is no self-healing, treatment is often carried out with neuroleptics.

The term psychosis was first coined in 1841 by Carl Friedrich Canstatt and again in 1845 by Ernst von Feuchtersleben. In 1846, Carl Friedrich Flemming wrote about the physical origin (somatogenesis): "Mental illness or psychosis takes root in the soul through the agency of the sense organ, and the next cause of mental illness is disease of the bodily organs."

A person suffering from psychosis was called a psychotic. The word "psychosis" appeared in 1875, along with the terms mental disorder, mental illness, and insanity, commonly used in psychiatry.

The purpose of the work: as the purpose of the work, pathological anatomy and biopsy examinations of 20 corpses brought to the Bureau of Pathological Anatomy of the Khorezm region from the dispensary of mental and nervous diseases of the region were targeted.

Obtained results: during scientific research, according to the results of pathologoanatomical and biopsy materials, the internal organs of 20 corpses were examined as macropreparation and micropreparation.

During the examinations, it is seen that there are pathological changes in the brain tissue, atrophy of the brain, the left brain is slightly smaller than the right brain in the large cerebral hemispheres.

Conclusions: in conclusion, it can be said that acute intoxication psychoses mainly occur in patients, the stress of the mother during pregnancy, the impact of infections on the immune system in childhood and its complications, the socialization and psychological development of the child, anatomical and functional deviations in the structure of the brain, mechanical effects on the brain, i.e. craniocerebral trauma or caused by tumors, hormone effects, as well as various somatic diseases.

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